

THE INFORMATION ABOUT THE JAMA MASJID BAYAZID BISTAMI IN THE NEIGHBOURHOOD OF BAYAZID BISTAMI IN KYZYLTEPO DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

One of the most famous Sufi saints known as Bayazid Tayfur ibn Isa al-Bistami (801–875) was born in the city of Bistam in Iran. Although much can be said about this great man, descriptions of him associated with gatherings of dervishes and spiritual assemblies cannot fully capture his essence. Bayazid Bastami is considered one of the founders of the Persian Sufi order and the Pir (spiritual guide) of the Tayfuriyya Sufi path. His grandfather was one of the Zoroastrians who converted to Islam, and Bayazid spent most of his life in Bistam. He passed away and was buried in his hometown. After his death, he was given the title “Sultan al-Arifin,” meaning “King of the Gnostics.” There is no reliable historical evidence that he ever visited Movarounnahr, particularly the region of Bukhara

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According to Bastami's teachings, during moments of deep spiritual ecstasy (hal), a person becomes so absorbed in divine love and intoxicated with the spirit of God that he loses all sense of self and merges completely with the divine essence. In such a state, the individual experiences “fana” (annihilation of the self) and ceases to exist in worldly form. He gave the description of a famous phrase “You are me, and I am you. he did so not out of pride, but because his consciousness was completely immersed in the divine presence. Bayazid Bastami left behind many wise sayings and served as an inspiration for later Sufi masters. Despite criticism from some who considered his words to contradict Islamic law, his followers believed that his expressions came from a state of divine ecstasy and were not to be taken literally.

Imam Abu Abdurrahman al-Sulami (936–1021) mentioned the full name of Sultan al-Arifin Hazrat Bayazid Bastami in his book “Tabaqat al-Sufiyya” as Abu Yazid (Bayazid) Tayfur

ibn Isa al-Sulami. This noble scholar was born in 801 CE in the city of Bistam (Bastam) in Iran, and because of this, he became known as Bastami.

According to narrations, Bayazid Bastami's mother experienced signs of his sainthood even while she was pregnant with him. It is said that whenever she ate doubtful or unlawful food, she would feel pain in her stomach until she got rid of it. From childhood, Bayazid attended a madrasa, and one day he met the great saint Shaiq al-Balkhi. When Shaiq al-Balkhi saw the young Bayazid, he greeted him with great respect and said, "In the future, this boy will become one of the greatest saints of his time."

It is also said that during his childhood, Bayazid used to serve his mother with great devotion. When his mother once told him, "My son, serve the Almighty faithfully, and He will make you a great man," Bayazid dedicated his entire life to the worship of Allah. Because of his piety and sincerity, Allah blessed Bayazid with extraordinary spiritual ranks and miracles. Tayfur Bayazid Bastami became one of the most famous and respected symbols of the Sufi world. His teachings on divine love, humility, and spiritual ecstasy influenced generations of Sufis. After his death, his resting place became a pilgrimage site visited by thousands of devotees. His wisdom and sayings encouraged believers to live with patience, humility, and sincere devotion to the Almighty. 105 -Source: Sadriiddin Salim Bukhari, Samad Azimov. "Hazrat Bayazid Bastami and the Spiritual Heritage of Navoi Region." Bukhara: "Bukhoro", 2010.

Bayazid Bistami received lessons from 113 spiritual masters. In the Naqshbandi order's "Silsilat al-Sharif," Bayazid Bistami is considered the spiritual guide of the sixth link, while the fifth link's guide was Hazrat Imam Ja'far al-Sadiq, may his secret be sanctified. According to Alisher Navoi's book "Nasayim al-Muhabbat," Bayazid Bistami, Abu al-Hasan Kharakani, and Bahauddin Naqshband are considered Uwaysi. Alisher Navoi explains the term "Uwaysi" as follows: "Any person who has not received spiritual education directly from a great saint, but has been spiritually trained through the soul of that saint or another pious predecessor, is called Uwaysi." It is known that the path of tariqat (spiritual order) is based on the purification of the soul. Hazrat Bayazid Bistami also devoted his days and nights to disciplining his nafs (ego). This practice is described as follows: "To suppress the desires of the nafs, to refrain from what it wants, and to force it to do what it dislikes, is the way to purify it through spiritual struggle." The foundation of tariqat is dhikr — the remembrance of Allah. Hazrat Bayazid said: "Before uttering the name of Allah with my tongue, I cleanse my mouth seventy times with pure clay." He also said: "How can one who lies or gossips mention the name of Allah with a deceitful tongue?" Hazrat Bayazid advised his disciples: "To harm the rights of a Muslim brother is not spiritual discipline. To neglect or disrespect a fellow Muslim because he does not greet you is not piety." Guard your tongue from speaking of anything other than Allah. O my Lord, protect me from gossip, lies, forbidden things, and evil speech. They say that the one who rescues a drowning person is a savior. Likewise, the masters of the Khwajagan order are also saviors .

Rescuers do not ask about a person's nationality, religion, race, or language — they simply strive to save human beings. Hazrat Bayazid Bistami devoted all his strength, knowledge, and skills to rescuing people from spiritual destruction. A person must protect

himself from the swamps of arrogance, greed, envy, and materialism, for those who fall into such moral corruption are bound to perish.

Hazrat Bayazid Bistami and his spiritual masters and disciples dedicated their lives to saving humanity from such destruction. For centuries, people have revered them as saints. Indeed, these great spiritual leaders played an important role in guiding society toward moral and spiritual perfection. In the village of Buston, located in the Kiziltepa district, there is a shrine of Hazrat Bayazid Bistami — a symbol of deep respect and reverence for this great saint. Until 1925, a majestic mosque stood on this sacred site, but it was destroyed during the Soviet era. In the ancient village of Buston in Kiziltepa district, the shrine of the scholar Bayazid Bistami remains, and hundreds of tourists from around the world visit this blessed place every year.

In 1990, a new mosque with northern and eastern wings and a spacious veranda was built on the site of the destroyed mosque through the efforts of local authorities and residents. A beautiful dome was erected over the symbolic grave, and the healing pool nearby was restored. Among those who contributed greatly to these works were Muzaffar Ismatov, Dilmurod Ergashev, and the master craftsman Bobonazar bobo. Today, the Bayazid Bistami Mosque serves as the main mosque of the district. Every Friday, hundreds of Muslims perform the noon prayer here in peace and unity. Visitors from Iran and Azerbaijan also frequently come to this shrine. The newly built mosque was completed under the initiative of the district's chief imam, There is also another shrine of Bayazid Bistami in the Shofirkon district

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